

IDIOMATIC REDUPLICATIONS IN THE DIALECTS OF AZERBAIJANI TURKISH

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Introduction

Language, as the cornerstone of human communication, is also a complex system that reflects cultural and social structures. One of the most significant functions of language is the effective conveyance of meaning. Meaning is a primary burden carried by language and is enriched through the structural and functional features of language. Various linguistic elements contribute to and strengthen the semantic and expressive dimensions of language. Among the most prominent of these elements are metaphors, metonymies, irony, idiomatic expressions, and reduplications.

In linguistics, studies on the various functional levels of language reveal the importance and position of idioms and reduplications within this system. Idioms and reduplications are key linguistic elements that demonstrate the richness and depth of language, reflect cultural values, and enhance communication. These elements illustrate that language is not merely a tool for communication but also a medium that conveys a society's thought patterns, emotions, and cultural heritage.

Idioms are among the most potent elements in terms of meaning within a language. Each idiom encapsulates the values, traditions, and lifestyles of the culture in which it is used. In this context, "Idioms are the vocabulary of a culture; each one is a reflection of the collective experiences of the past" [Seidl & McMordie, 1988.-12]. These expressions strengthen narration and enhance the persuasiveness of language. According to Moon [1998]"Idioms increase the flexibility and power of language in expressing thoughts and feelings" [p. 42]. In Turkish, which is rich in the number of idiomatic expressions, various definitions have been proposed for idioms. In the Turkish Dictionary, idioms are defined as "a fixed phrase that generally carries a meaning somewhat different from its literal sense; a phrase" [TS: 996]. Buran [2015] defines them as "Fixed phrases, consisting of at least two words, with new and specific meanings beyond their literal meanings, and not bound by a particular rule" [p. 97]. In Western languages, idioms are referred to as *locution* in French; *locution, idiom, formula, expression* in English; *ausdruck, redensart* in German; *frazeologizm, obraznoye, virajeniye* in Russian; and as *darbimesel, ta'bir, and istilah* in Ottoman Turkish [Sinan A. T., 2015. - 17]. Common features of the definitions made for

idioms include their formation as phrases, the detachment of at least one of the words forming the idiom from its literal meaning, and the creation of a different meaning.

Yalçın and Çalışır [2012] categorize the syntactic and morphological formations of idioms as follows: "Those formed by one or more nouns with a verb, those formed by one or more nouns with an auxiliary verb, those fixed in the form of a verbal group, those fixed in the form of a compound, those fixed in the form of a predicate group, those fixed with a case suffix, and those formed by reduplications" [p. 137-139].

Reduplications within idioms can be categorized as follows: those formed by the repetition of the same word, those formed by the repetition of synonymous or nearly synonymous words, those formed by the repetition of antonyms, those formed by the repetition of words based on phonetic similarity, and those formed by the repetition of onomatopoeic words [Yalçın & Çalışır, 2012. - 140].

Idiomatic reduplications are linguistic structures formed by the combination of two or more words that, when used together, acquire a new and fixed meaning. These structures are one of the conventional and fixed elements of language and are frequently encountered in everyday spoken language. For instance, reduplications such as "crooked" or "broken" convey meanings that go beyond the individual meanings of the words, expressing more abstract and complex ideas [Aksoy Ö. A., 2005. - 96]. These reduplications contribute to the structural richness of the language while also enhancing its aesthetic dimension.

While idioms strengthen the pragmatic function of language, reduplications emphasize the phonological and morphological richness of the language. Idiomatic reduplications, emerging from the combination of these two linguistic structures, represent an important category that reflects the evolutionary processes of language. These structures are critical for understanding the depth and richness of the Turkish lexicon. Idiomatic reduplications not only increase the semantic depth of the language but also allow for the more intense expression of a particular situation, feeling, or phenomenon. Such expressions often contain figurative meanings, thereby multiplying the layers of meaning within the language [Göksel & Kerslake, 2005. - 214].

The prevalence of these elements highlights the richness of Turkish in diversifying the possibilities of expression. Particularly in dialects, these elements are significant due to their archaic features. Idiomatic reduplications are a valuable data source for understanding how language has evolved and functioned in its evolutionary process. Furthermore, the use of idiomatic reduplications within a cultural context is an important indicator reflecting the values and thought structures of the society in which the language exists.

When we examine idiomatic reduplications in the dialects of Azerbaijani Turkish, a parallel situation with general Turkish will be observed. Forty-four of these elements are formed by the repetition of the same word; forty-three by the repetition of synonymous or nearly synonymous words; fourteen by the repetition of words based on phonetic similarity; four by the repetition of antonyms; and two by the repetition of onomatopoeic words. Considering the structure of the reduplicated words, it is natural that idiomatic reduplications formed by the repetition of the same word, i.e., complete reduplications, are predominant. This is because a large portion of reduplications is formed in this way. The percentage distribution of the examined idiomatic reduplications is as follows:

Graphic1.Proportional Distribution of Idiomatic Reduplications in the Dialects of Azerbaijani Turkish

Conclusion

In this study, which examines idiomatic reduplications in the dialects of Azerbaijani Turkish, a total of 175 dialects were analyzed, leading to the identification of 107 examples of idiomatic reduplications. A brief dictionary, in which these examples are alphabetically listed, is included in the appendix of this study.

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-A-

1. **Acı-qıcı (ver-):** To make ambitious [ADNRŞ: 54]
2. **Adar-madar:** The only, the sole, the lonely [ADL: 2]
3. **Ağın-dağın (çıkart-):** Exaggerating [ADNRŞ: 57]
4. **Ağzabuğuz:** Replete [ADNRŞ: 58]
5. **Ağ-qızıl:** Property [ADNRŞ: 59]
6. **Ağzaboğaz:** Brim [ADL: 6]
7. **Ağzabuğuz:** Brim [ADL: 6]
8. **Aldım-verdim:** First meeting with the girl's house, interruption [ADNRŞ: 64]
9. **Altı-beş (vır-):** Nonsense, to stumble [ADNRŞ: 65]
10. **Alhaşığ-çalhaşığ:** Mutually [ADNRŞ: 64]
11. **Arpa-bığda:** Giving birth to boys and girls in turn [ADDŞXTL: 108]
12. **Arpa-bığda:** Giving birth to boys and girls in turn [ADNRŞ: 69]
13. **Arpa-buğda:** Giving birth to boys and girls in turn [ADL: 17]
14. **Atım-atım (atıl-):** Being fit [ADNRŞ: 71]
15. **Ay-ıldız:** Precious piece [ADL: 22]

16. **Ayıl-mayıl (ol-):**Admiration [ADL: 22]

-B-

17. **Baş-göz (êlê-):** Marrying [ADNDL: 70]

18. **Baş-göz (ol-/eyle-):** Marriage, to marry [ADNRŞ: 80]

19. **Boğıla-boğıla:** Wood smoldering [ADNRŞ: 93]

-C-

20. **Cağ cağ (ol-):** Split into pieces, torn to pieces [ADL: 69]

-Ç-

21. **Çinem-çinem:**Exchange ideas [ADL: 104]

-D-

22. **Dar-düdük:** Very narrow, tight [TŞİL: 40]

23. **Daşbaş:** Illegal income [TŞİL: 40]

24. **Dege-darağ (düzelt-):** repeating the work done [ADNDL: 114]

25. **Den-duz (eyle-):** Preparing food [ADNRŞ: 120]

26. **Denin-duzum (ver-):** Admonish [ADNRŞ: 121]

27. **Doğdi-bitti:**From ancestors, grandfathers [ADL: 148]

28. **Döydağ-döydağ:** Stand tall like a pole [ADNDL: 122]

29. **Düz-qoş (ele-):** Set right [ADNRŞ: 129]

-E-

30. **Edeli-dedeli:** In accordance with tradition [ADNRŞ: 131]

31. **Edili-düdülü:**Everything is in its proper place and in accordance with the rules[ADL: 166]

32. **Efci-efci:**Talking pointlessly [ADL: 166]

33. **Ekec-ekec:**To boast [ADL: 167]

34. **El-ayağ (ele-):** Take action [ADNRŞ: 133]

35. **El-eyah:**Doing any job quickly [ADL: 169]

36. **Elah-salah:**Empty, single, unemployed, vagabond [ADL: 168]

37. **Eleşen-küleşen:**With difficulty [ADL: 169]

38. **Eli-qolı (soyu-):** Fatigue [ADNRŞ: 134]

39. **Ellem-qellem:** Mixed [ADNDL: 131]

40. **Elli-eyağlı:** Skilled [ADNRŞ: 135]

41. **Elli-qollı:** Skilled[ADNRŞ: 135]

42. **Encim-ñıncım (eyle-):** To scrutinise [ADNRŞ: 135]

43. **Enecer-sütecer:** The second child born before the first one reached adulthood [ADL: 173]

44. **Evelen-gevelen:**Empty, unnecessary, out of place [ADL: 179].

45. **Evelen-gevelen:** Meaningless, empty words [ADNRŞ: 138]

46. **Ezvay-ezvay:** Talking bitterly [ADNRŞ: 139]

47. **Ezzavara-ezzavara:** Helplessly [ADNRŞ: 139]

-G-

48. **Geldi-gèdergi:** Foreign [ADNDL: 140]

-H-

49. **Hayda-hayduya (götür-):** To ridicule [ADNDL: 156]

50. **Hellem-qellem:** Fraudulent person [ADNRŞ: 150]

51. **Hersimpers (ol-):**To be enchanted [ADL: 222]

52. **Hersipers (ol-):** To be enchanted [ADL: 222]

53. **Hèrti-pèrti:** A large, rude person [ADNDL: 151]

54. **Hır-zır (bilme-):** Illiteracy [ADNRŞ: 151]

55. **Hırım-zırım (ol-):** To be angry and sad [ADL: 225]

56. **Hintil-mintil (ol-):**To be like a drunk [ADL: 226]

57. **Hoç-hoçilik:** A gossip, a person who spreads gossip [ADL: 226]

58. **Hor-hori:**Idle talker, chatterbox [ADL: 228]

-H -

59. **Hıncam-hıncam (èle-):**To crush [ADL: 244]

60. **Hozu-hozu (gez-):** To hold one's head high [ADNDL: 164]

-K-

61. **Kedi-kedi (danış-):**Speaking in a way that is not appropriate for one's age [ADL: 271]

62. **Kelle-kelle:** To talk big, to brag [ADNRŞ: 161]

63. **Kertdeş-kertdeş (danış-):** To talk nonsense [ADL: 278]

64. **Keze-küze (danış-):**To talk nonsense [ADL: 279]

65. **Köntöy-köntöy (danış-):**To speak rudely, badly [ADL: 288]

-Q-

66. **Qadı-qadı (danış-):** To boast [konuşmak] [ADL: 300]

67. **Qannı-qannı:** Ambitious, spiteful [ADNRŞ: 172]

68. **Qart-qart:** To boast [ADNRŞ: 175]

69. **Qat-qar (èle-):** To mix [ADL: 315]

70. **Qayım-qedim (ol-):** Gaining respect [ADNDL: 196]

71. **Qazı-qazı (danış-):** To boast [ADL: 318]

72. **Qazı-qazı (danış-):** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADNRŞ: 176]

73. **Qılıs-qılıs (danış-):** To talk nonsense [ADL: 326]

74. **Qol-qayı:** Kin, relative [ADMSŞ: 336]

-L-

75. **Lebbeleb:** Full to the brim [ADL: 358]

76. **Ledim-ledim:** Blankly [ADL: 360]

77. **Leş-leş:** Empty-handed, unemployed [ADL: 359]

78. **Leyla-leyla:**In a sad way [ADL: 359]

79. **Lobbaz-lobbaz (danış-):** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADL: 369]

-M-

80. **Mavala-mavala (gal-):** In a hungry way [ADL: 382]

-N-

81. **Nağız-nağız:** Thoughtless, irrelevant [ADL: 409]

82. **Nem-nüm (ele-):** To be coy [TŞİL: 115]

-O-

83. **Ornac-ornac (danış-):** To boast [ADL: 429]

84. **Ozana-ozana (gez-):** Empty-handed, unemployed [ADL: 432]

85. **Ozan-qazan:** To be confused [ADL: 432]

86. **Otar-suvar (ele-):** To cheat [ADNDL: 228]

87. **Oyma-büzme:** Mowing and sewing irregularly [ADNRŞ: 203]

88. **Ozana-cazana (gel-):** To be fed up [ADNRŞ: 203]

89. **Ozan-cazan (ol-):** Talking too much [ADNRŞ: 203]

-Ö-

90. **Ögec-ögec:** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADL: 434]

91. **Ölüm-zulum:** With difficulty [ADNRŞ: 204]

92. **Örnec-örnec:** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADL: 436]

-P-

93. **Pıl-pıl (ol-):** To break, to shatter [ADL: 453]

-S-

94. **Saf-saf (ol-):** To be full of holes [ADL: 468]

-Ş-

95. **Şahda-şeyid (ol-):** Getting very tired [ADNDL: 253]

96. **Şiltih-şiltih (èle-):** Tear to pieces [ADL: 531]

-T-

97. **Tepiy-tepiye (dur-):** To come face to face [ADNRŞ: 235]

98. **Ter-quru (yığ-):** Arranging the bread alternately hot and dry [ADNDL: 271]

-U-

99. **Urnac-urnac (danış-):** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADL: 594]

100. **Urnac-urnac (danış-):** To speak with a swagger and boast [ADMŞ: 356]

-Ü-

101. **Ürey-göbey (tüş-):** Being very scared [ADNRŞ: 244]

-Y-

102. **Yağmac-bılamac:** Slapdash [ADL: 618]

103. **Yencih'-yencih' (danış-):** Speaking without thinking [ADL: 631]

- 104. Yerri-yatađlı:** A young man who has reached puberty [ADNRŞ: 255]
105. Yıđımlı-derimli: Frugal [ADNRŞ: 255]
106. Yıđın-derinni: Prudent [ADND: 247]

-Z-

- 107. Zeneki-zeneki (danıř-):** To speak like a child, in a childish way [ADL:
642]